

Studies of some Metal Chelates of Ketoanils

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Manuscript received 21 January 1993, revised 27 January 1994, accepted 9 February 1994

Chelates of Ru^{III}, Rh^{III}, Pd^{II}, Os^{IV}, Ir^{III} and Pt^{IV} with *p*-dimethylamino-, *p*-diethylamino-, *p*-chloro-, *p*-bromo- and *p*-iodo-anils of 2-thiophene glyoxal have been prepared. In electrolytic square-planar complexes of Pd^{II} and octahedral complexes of other metal ions, ligands are coordinated through thienyl sulphur and carbonyl oxygen in quinonoid structure.

Considerable interest attached with the chemistry of ketoanils, products of glyoxals and primary amines, owes to their biochemical properties¹ and uses, as analytical reagents², as novel ligands³⁻⁵ and as starting materials in the synthesis of heterocyclics⁶. Peculiar coordination features of ketoanils in forming complexes of generally unusual stereochemistries and isomeric compositions, governed, most probably, by the nature and position of their substituted group which could significantly influence the charge density at carbonyl oxygen, i.e. coordination activity of the ligand as a whole, have entrusted us to synthesise and report herein a few complexes of platinum group noble metals, relatively less investigated systems, with *p*-dimethylamino-, *p*-diethylamino-, *p*-chloro-, *p*-bromo- and *p*-iodo-anils of 2-thiopheneglyoxal (abbreviated as DMATG, DEATG, CATG, BATG and IATG respectively).

Results and Discussion

The analytical data consistent with the proposed stoichiometries of the complexes are noted in Table 1. Molecular conductivity values reveal^{7,8} univalent (1 : 2) electrolytic nature of Ru(C₁₄H₁₂N₂OS)₂Cl₃·H₂O, Ru(C₁₂H₉NOSI)₂Cl₃·H₂O, Os-(C₁₄H₁₂N₂OS)₂(OH)₄ and all the Pd^{II} and Pt^{IV} complexes, and uni-univalent (1 : 1) nature of rest of the Ru^{III}, Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} complexes in methylcyanide. The low Λ_M values obtained generally may be attributed⁷ to large cations.

Ketoanils with electron donor substituent in *para*-position exist generally in two tautomeric forms,

(I) and (II), with predominance of quinonoid form (II) in solution. Metal ions may be expected to coordinate through the azomethine nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen of form (II). In 2-thiopheneglyoxal anils thiene sulphur is an additional coordination centre.

where X and R are N(CH₃)₂, N(C₂H₅)₂, Cl, Br, I and C₄H₃S respectively.

The IR spectra of the ligands and their complexes, which exhibit considerable lowering in frequency and intensity of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ and thienyl $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}}$ groups bands from ca. 1666 to ca. 1630 cm⁻¹⁵ and from ca. 665 to ca. 645 cm⁻¹¹⁰ respectively, and undisplaced position of azomethine peak of ligands (ca. 1618 cm⁻¹) on complexation, indicate biligancy of ketoanils through their carbonyl and thienyl groups and azomethine donor group does not seem to participate in coordination, probably due to its remote position from coordinating groups. Appearance of new bands at 405-565 (M-O)⁵ and ~ 227 cm⁻¹ (M-S)⁵ support the above inference. The change in band structure, doublet to singlet, and/or increase in frequency of band for 1 : 4 disubstitution from ca. 822 to ca. 830 cm⁻¹, and disappearance or lowering in frequency of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ (aromatic) bands of ligands (ca. 1510, 1542 and 1562 cm⁻¹) on chelation evidently show molecular rearrangement in ligands during metal-ligand interaction, i.e. change of benzenoid structure (I) to quinonoid unit (II), which

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour, M.p. °C)	Analysis(%) : Found/(Calcd.)				M	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ mol^{-1}	10 Dq cm^{-1}	Racah's parameters		β	LFSE kcal mol^{-1}
	C	H	N	Cl				B cm^{-1}	C cm^{-1}		
[Ru(C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS) ₂ Cl(H ₂ O)]Cl ₂ (Brown, 198)	44.86 (45.52)	3.39 3.52	7.30 7.55	14.19 14.34	13.78 13.63	377.9	17 385	340.9	1 363.5	—	45.77
[Ru(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl.H ₂ O (Violet, 195)	47.78 (48.35)	3.99 4.28	6.91 7.03	13.19 13.34	12.61 12.68	118.4	17 353	340.3	1 361.0	—	45.70
[Ru(C ₁₂ H ₉ NOSCl) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl.H ₂ O (Brown, 188)	40.00 (39.60)	2.93 2.75	3.66 3.87	14.58 14.68	13.81 13.95	135.0	23 715	465.0	1 860.0	—	62.44
[Ru(C ₁₂ H ₉ NOSBr) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl.H ₂ O (Brown, 192)	34.66 (35.29)	2.65 2.45	3.38 3.44	13.22 13.08	12.29 12.43	143.5	15 848	310.8	1 243.0	—	41.20
[Ru(C ₁₂ H ₉ NOS I) ₂ Cl(H ₂ O)]Cl ₂ (Dark orange, 176)	32.09 (31.64)	2.24 2.20	2.90 3.09	11.63 11.72	11.06 11.14	243.2	16 467	322.9	1 291.5	—	43.36
[Rh(C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl.H ₂ O (Brown, 218)	46.01 (45.44)	3.33 3.52	7.61 7.53	14.18 14.31	13.76 13.85	132.3	27 584	405.9	3 774.5	0.56	97.17
[Pd(C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS) ₂]Cl ₂ (Brown, 201)	49.21 (48.72)	3.51 3.48	8.20 8.08	10.13 10.23	15.21 15.35	383.1	—	—	—	—	—
[Pd(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS) ₂]Cl ₂ (Brown, 208)	51.32 (51.50)	4.42 4.29	7.28 7.47	13.19 13.34	14.02 14.20	137.9	—	—	—	—	—
[Pd(C ₁₂ H ₉ NOSCl) ₂]Cl ₂ (Brown green, 196)	42.11 (42.43)	2.51 2.65	4.02 4.14	10.68 10.52	15.62 15.73	149.4	—	—	—	—	—
[Pd(C ₁₂ H ₉ NOSBr) ₂]Cl ₂ (Brown, 186)	37.69 (37.52)	2.39 2.35	3.58 3.66	9.40 9.27	13.74 13.91	265.9	—	—	—	—	—
[Pd(C ₁₂ H ₉ NOSI) ₂]Cl ₂ (Brown, 179)	32.92 (32.42)	2.05 2.09	3.11 3.26	8.14 8.25	12.22 12.39	140.1	—	—	—	—	—
[Os(C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS) ₂ (OH) ₂](OH) ₂ (Violet, 205)	44.00 (43.64)	3.51 3.64	7.10 7.23)	—	—	1 44.5	—	—	—	—	—
[Ir(C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl (Brown, 216)	41.93 (41.41)	3.00 2.96	6.98 6.87	12.96 13.60	23.44 23.60	55.4	28 919	486.7	3 919.0	0.74	101.87
[Ir(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl (Gray, 203)	43.88 (44.27)	3.49 3.69	6.26 6.43	12.00 12.22	21.97 22.08)	65.3	26 189	469.6	2 932.5	0.71	105.95
[Ir(C ₁₂ H ₉ NOSBr) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl (Brown, 200)	32.05 (32.38)	1.90 2.02	3.40 3.16	12.08 12.00	21.56 21.68)	74.7	23 913	330.5	2 174.0	0.50	109.67
[Ir(C ₁₂ H ₉ NOSI) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl (Brown, 187)	28.89 (29.28)	2.08 1.83	3.00 2.86	10.75 10.85	19.48 19.61)	54.0	24 102	359.4	2 825.5	0.54	95.65
[Pt(C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂ (Brown, 250)	39.29 (39.58)	2.69 2.83	6.75 6.57	16.49 16.63	22.73 22.87)	147.4	29 370	486.7	4 370.0	—	94.65
[Pt(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂ (Brown, 238)	42.88 (42.43)	3.37 3.54	6.00 6.16	15.39 15.60	21.32 21.46)	271.0	27 810	478.1	3 714.5	—	99.07
[Pt(C ₁₂ H ₉ NOSBr) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂ (Gray brown, 210)	30.67 (31.07)	1.82 1.94	2.89 3.03	15.19 15.33	20.98 21.10)	243.0	26 303	400.7	3 303.0	—	99.24

consequently increases coordination activity of the carbonyl group.

All the bis-ligand complexes display one or two terminal M–Cl stretching bands in 305–330 cm^{-1} region⁹ except Os^{IV} and Pd^{II} compounds. Since octahedral complexes of ML₂X₂ type (where L and X are bidentate ligand and monodentate halogen respectively) exhibit two terminal M–X stretching bands in C_{2v} (*cis*) symmetry and one band in D_{4h} (*trans*) symmetry generally, *cis*-configuration may be proposed⁹ to Ru(C₁₂H₉NOSCl)₂Cl₂.H₂O, whereas

other complexes seem to obtain *trans*-symmetry^{6,9}. In some cases broad M–Cl peak structure, which could be attributed to accidental degeneracy of two normal modes of a *cis*-isomer, lead us to suggest their *cis*-configuration.

Additional M–O stretching bands^{4,10} at 235, 250 and 215 cm^{-1} , at 375 and at 310 cm^{-1} in Ru(C₁₄H₁₂N₂OS)₂Cl₃.H₂O, Ru(C₁₂H₉NOSI)₂Cl₃.H₂O and Os(C₁₄H₁₂N₂OS)₂(OH)₄ respectively, indicate presence of other oxygen donor group than ketoanils, probably H₂O/OH, in the coordination

sphere. One or two bands at 900–985 cm^{-1} corresponding to twisting, rocking and wagging vibrations of HOH or bending vibrations of OH¹⁰, Λ_M values and stability upto 190° of these complexes confirm coordination of H₂O and OH in the Ru^{III} and Os^{IV} complexes respectively. Other hydrated complexes, however, displayed bands at 3 300–3 430 and 1 610–1 635 cm^{-1} , attributable to symmetric and antisymmetric stretching and bending vibrations respectively, of their lattice water^{4,10}. As δ_{OH_2} band interferes with $\nu_{\text{C=O}} / \nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band (s) at 1 610–1 635 cm^{-1} , identification of carbonyl and azomethine groups in the hydrated complexes was done after their dehydration at $\sim 90^\circ$. Anhydrous samples exhibited more sharp bands of lower frequencies (1 600–1 630 cm^{-1}) than the hydrated compounds.

The Ru^{III} complexes, which displayed magnetic moments (1.58–1.66 B.M) corresponding to one unpaired electron, are simple paramagnetics. Electronic spectra displaying seven ligand field bands at ca. 13 249, 16 099, 17 700, 19 332, 20 736, 25 011 and 28 700 cm^{-1} attributable to *d-d* electronic transitions from ²T_{2g} ground state to excited states ⁴T_{1g}, ⁴T_{2g}, ²A_{1g}, ²A_{2g}, ²E_g, ²T_{1g} and ²T_{2g} respectively^{10,11}, are characteristic of octahedral geometry of isoelectronic (*d*⁵) ions. Electronic spectral band splitting patterns which are identical, are consistent with magnetic moments of the complexes. Ligand field parameters calculated by standard methods¹² are noted in Table 1. One or two charge transfer bands were observed at ca. 37 387 and 40 816 cm^{-1} ¹⁰.

The diamagnetism exhibited by the Pd^{II} complexes is indicative of their low-spin square-planar configuration. Electronic spectral bands at ca. 18 366, 21 244 and 22 808 cm^{-1} corresponding to ¹A_{2g} ← ¹A_{1g}, ¹B_{1g} ← ¹A_{1g} and ¹E_{1g} ← ¹A_{1g} transitions respectively, confirm square-planar stereochemistry¹³. Based on the facts that in square-planar complexes of *d*⁸-configuration involving ligands having no π orbitals, two metal ← ligand charge transfer bands are spaced at energy difference of $\sim 10\,000$ cm^{-1} , the last two bands of high intensity at ca. 32 484 and 41 907 cm^{-1} can be assigned¹³ to spin-allowed charge transfer transitions, ¹A_{2u} ← ¹A_{1g} and ¹E_u ← ¹A_{1g} respectively.

In the osmium complex, Os^{VIII}, the starting

material, seems to be reduced to Os^{IV}, by DMATG in alkaline medium. For Os^{IV} one would expect a paramagnetism corresponding to two spin-free electrons but due to large values of λ ($\sim 2\,000$ cm^{-1}) in octahedral Os^{IV} complexes their magnetic moments are obtained generally in 1.2–1.7 B.M. range as predicted^{14,15}. The magnetic moment (1.22 B.M.) of Os(C₁₄H₁₂N₂OS)₂(OH)₄, indicative^{15,16} of Os^{IV} state in octahedral environment of ligand is in agreement with analysis and conductance results. A doublet band at 18 152 cm^{-1} corresponding¹⁷ to ¹A_{1g} ← ³E_g transition also supports tetravalent oxidation state of osmium in the complex; another band at 28 571 cm^{-1} , however, is due to M ← L charge transfer.

The ligand field bands observed in the Rh^{III}, Ir^{III} and Pt^{IV} complexes are analogous¹⁵ to those observed in isoelectronic Co^{III} and Ru^{II} complexes of octahedrally disposed strong ligand fields. The spectra showed two spin-forbidden, ³T_{1g} ← ¹A_{1g} and ³T_{2g} ← ¹A_{1g} and two spin-allowed, ¹T_{1g} ← ¹A_{1g} and ¹T_{2g} ← ¹A_{1g} transitions at ca. 16 644 and 19 136 cm^{-1} and at ca. 23 397 and 30 232 cm^{-1} respectively, in each case as theoretically expected. In addition to *d-d* transition bands one or two M ← L charge transfer bands¹⁰ of high intensity at ca. 36 200 and 40 000 cm^{-1} were also observed in each spectrum. Observed diamagnetism of these complexes, indicative of their low-spin *d*⁶-octahedral stereochemistry, supports *d-d* bands splitting pattern. The 10 *Dq* values (Table 1) of the complexes of each metal ion, forming an order identical to those in $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and electron repelling ability of *para*-substituted group of ligands, support the direct effect of electron-repelling ability of *para*-substituents on coordination activity of carbonyl group of ketoanils.

Experimental

The ketoanils¹⁸ were precipitated while mixing solutions of 2-thiopheneglyoxal (1 mol) and corresponding amine (1 mol) in ether. The precipitates after washing with ether were crystallised from benzene or acetone.

For the preparation of complexes, solutions of ligand (2 mol) and metal compounds (1 mol) in acetone-water (19 : 1, v/v) were mixed together. While mixing the reactants most of the complexes

were precipitated. Complexes of Ru^{III} with CATG, Pd^{II} with all the ligands and Os^{IV}-DMATG, which could not be precipitated, were isolated after refluxing and concentrating, and by raising pH upto 11 with NaOH solution of the reaction mixtures respectively. Products were washed with ether and chloroform successively and/or crystallised, and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Laboratory reagents (B.D.H.) and OsO₄ and chlorides of other metals (Johnson Metthey) were used as such.

Nitrogen and metal contents were estimated microanalytically at C.D.R.I., Lucknow, whereas chlorine was estimated as AgCl gravimetrically. Osmium complex was not analysed owing to non-availability of a suitable method for estimation of its metal content. Melting points of the complexes were determined in open glass capillaries. Conductance was measured with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge using a dip-type cell with a cell constant of 0.61. Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (methyl cyanide) on a Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility of powdered solids was measured with a Gouy balance at room temperature using CoHg(SCN)₄ as calibrant.

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